

A CASE STUDY ON PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GROUND WATER AND SOIL SAMPLES OF MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE DUMP YARD

Priyanka Gaur¹, Dr. Ravi Bhatnagar²

¹Research Scholar, SunRise University, Alwar (Raj.) India

²Research Supervisor, SunRise University, Alwar (Raj.) India

ABSTRACT

The pace urbanisation in India has been rapidly increasing, with about 30% of the total population already living in urban areas. Studies predict that, by 2025 AD, over 55% of India's population will be urban and there will be over 50 cities with population excess of one million. Urbanization, along with increased industrialisation and motorization, has severely damaged urban environment and health of people. To minimize these ill effects, it is necessary to have accurate, timely, reliable information and performance indicators that can indicate the status of health and environment in urban areas, which can be used to take corrective and preventive measures to improve the quality of urban life. The distinctive character of urbanization is high density of population, high-energy consumption and huge generation of high quality wastes and effluents from both industries and domestic environment. The splendid achievements in the field of science and technology made triumphant progress in the urbanisation. According to ministry of urban affairs, government of India estimated 0.5 kg (app.) of waster generated per person per day.

The problem of municipal solid waste management has acquired alarming dimensions in our country especially over the last decade. Before that, waste management was hardly considered as an issue of concern as the wastes could be easily disposed off in an environmentally safe manner within the generation premises. However, with the passage of time, due to changing life styles of people coupled with urbanization and industrialisation the waste characteristics have altered making them a little tricky to be managed. In this paper an attempt has been made to highlight the physico-chemical characteristics of ground water and soil samples around municipal dump yard and to assess whether the water is suitable for drinking purpose.

Keywords: Physicochemical, Ground water, Solid Waste Dump Yard

INTRODUCTION

Waste is defined as “discarded material judged to be of no value for ordinary or normal use”. The term “solid waste” usually refers to waste that is solid, including semi liquid or wet waste with sufficient moisture content to be free flowing. Solid wastes generated can be both biodegradable and non bio-degradable.

Urban solid waste can be categorized as below depending upon the source of generation table 1.

Table 1: Category of Urban Solid waste:

S.No.	Category	Source	Percentage
1	Domestic waste	Residential Houses	54%
2	Trade Waste	Trade, Hawker, Shops, Petrol pumps, Markets, Offices, Halls, Hotel	31%
3	Clinical Waste	Hospitals and Nursing Homes	2%
4	Other waste including Industrial Waste.	Drain Silt, Building activity waste, Street Sweeping, Wastes from Industries	13%

Much information is available about the waste composition, except a few studies, which are often quoted everywhere. According to the studies of Bhide and Sundersan, 1983 and EPTRI, 1995 the organic matter percentage has remained almost static at 41% in past three decades, but the recyclables have increased from 9.56% to 17.18%. Amongst various recyclables, plastics had a quantum jump from 0.69% to 3.9% more than 5 fold increases with in last twenty years. Plastics due to their unique properties of flexibility, high impacts strength, resistance to corrosion, rigidity have replaced the valuable natural resources like wood and metals resulting in a ten-fold increase during the 2008-2018 decade alone. Of the current consumption figure of 1.9 million tonnes, 15% of plastics are used by the packaging sector. This packaging, reaches the waste bin as the post consumer waste. Most of this does not have a good recycling value and hence is disposed off by municipalities as a part of the kitchen waste.

Materials and Methods:

The actual area of the study is a dumping yard at 17^o42' North latitude and 83^o01' East longitude is surrounding a village. The dumping yard is situated in North East corner of the city. About 755 of the population residing near and around this area utilize the ground water for drinking and agriculture and other purposes.

The aim of the study is to assess physico-chemical characteristics of ground water and soil near the dump yard and to conclude whether the water, soil is suitable for drinking and agriculture purposes. For this reason 14 physico-chemical parameters of water and soil such as pH, Conductivity, Hardness, Calcium, Magnesium, Total Dissolved Solids, Chlorides, Sulphates, Nitrates, COD, DO, Phosphates, Organic Carbon, Organic matter, potassuim, Available Nitrogen are selected and all samples are analysed as per standard procedures.

PREPARATION OF WATER AND SOIL SAMPLES FOR CHEMICAL ANALYSIS:

Water

The water samples were collected from both wells and bore wells in upstream and downstream of solid waste dumping yard. The samples were collected once in a month for a period of three

months. All the samples are properly labeled indicating the source of the sample, time and date of collection. The samples were brought to the laboratory in ice containers and analysed the parameters within 48 hours of collection. In case of DO the samples were fixed in the site itself and analysed in the laboratory within 6 hours.

Solid waste

The soil and solid waste samples were collected upto 10 cm of depth and brought to laboratory. The samples were air dried and crushed and sieved through 2 mm. The samples were stored in polythene bottles and used for chemical analysis.

Preparation of soil extract

100 g of sieved soil is dissolved in 500 ml of distilled water and is stirred for about 30 minutes. Then the solution is allowed to settle down and centrifuged. The supernatant solution of centrifugal soil extract was used to analyse pH, conductivity, chlorides, alkalinity, sulphates and nitrates in soil waste.

Water quality Index

Water Quality Index indicates a single number (like a grade) that expresses the overall water quality at a certain location and time based on several water quality parameters. It is also defined as a rating reflecting the composite influence of different water quality parameters on the overall quality of water. According to the concept of indices to represent gradation in water quality was first proposed by Horton (1965). The use of an index to grade water quality is a controversial among water quality scientists.

The main objective of water quality index is to turn complex water quality data into information that is understandable and useable by the public. Water quality index based on some very important parameters can provide a simple indicator of water quality. It gives the public a general idea of the possible problems with water in a particular region. The indices are among the most effective ways to communicate the information on water quality trends to the public or to the policy makers and water quality management.

For calculation of WQI, selection of parameters has great importance. Since selection of too many parameters might widen the quality index and importance of various parameters depends on the intended use of water, ten physico-chemical parameters namely pH, Hardness, Calcium, Magnesium, Total dissolved solids, chlorides, sulphates, Nitrates, Chemical Oxygen Demand and dissolved Oxygen are used to calculate WQI.

WQI is calculated from the following equation:

Weighted arithmetic index method has been used for calculation of WQI. The **unit weight (Wi)** has been found out by using the formulae:

$$W_i = \frac{k}{S_i}$$

Where

k = proportionality constant

S_i = Standard permissible value of i^{th} parameter

W_i = unit weight of i^{th} parameter

Water Quality Index

$$WQI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n q_i W_i}{\sum_{k=0}^n W_i}$$

Where

q_i = Sub Index, $q_i = 100[v_i/s_i]$

V_i = observed value, n= number of parameters taken

S_i = standard value of i^{th} parameter

For pH,

$$q_{pH} = 100[(v_{pH} - 7.0) / 8.5 - 7.0]$$

For Dissolved Oxygen,

$$q_{DO} = 100[(v_{DO} - 14.6)/5 - 14.6]$$

After compiling the results, the concentration of each pollutant was converted into a WQI. The pollutant with the highest WQI became the overall WQI for a particular location. The higher the WQI value, the greater is the level of water pollution, and greater the damage to health.

The WQI scale was divided into five categories, each category describes the range of water quality and its associated potential health effects. The index was health-based description to provide meaningful information to the public. The five levels of WQI are depicted in Table 2.

Table 2: Water Quality Index (WQI) Range

WQI	Grade	Status
0-25	A	Quality of water is excellent
26-50	B	Quality of water is good
51-75	C	Quality of water is poor
75-100	D	Quality of water is very poor
100 and Above	E	Water is undesirable for drinking

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The physico-chemical characteristics of sampling stations were analysed and the observations are as follows:

Physico-Chemical Analysis of Ground Water:

The result of well and bore water sample are given in Table No.3.

Table 3: Characteristics of Bore Waters collected from Dumping Yard

S.No	Parameter	Sample 1	Sample 2
1	pH	7.18	6.59
2	Conductivity (mMhos/cm)	0.15	0.20
3	Hardness	560	700
4	Calcium	200	260
5	Magnesium	360	440
6	Total Dissolved Solids	560	520
7	Chemical Oxygen Demand	36	28
8	Phosphates	0.233	0.83
9	Sulphates	100	124
10	Nitrates	1.064	1.418
11	Chlorides	239.99	359.99
12	Dissolved Oxygen	3.0	1.9

Note: All values are exposed in ppm except pH and conductivity

Sample 1 : Bore well present inside the plant

Sample 2: Bore well near dumping yard

The pH of ground water is governed by CO₂- bicarbonate- carbonate equilibrium. Though pH has no direct effect on human health, all biochemical reactions are sensitive to the variations of pH. The permissible limit of pH value of drinking water is specified as 6.5-8.5. The pH of the observed groundwater samples are 6.59 and 7.18 indicating their acceptability.

The electrical conductivity is a very important parameter for determining water quality for drinking and agricultural purposes. The ideal value of electrical conductivity is 2.4milliMhos/cm. The values are observed within the range i.e., 0.15-0.20milliMhos/cm.

Total dissolved solids in the study area recorded as 560 and 520 ppm. The acceptable value of TDS in groundwater is 500ppm. The total dissolved solids of the study area fall in the prescribed range.

The COD in all the samples from the study area is reasonably high. The values range from 26-38 ppm. This indicates the presence of oxidizable impurities in water samples.

Hardness is a prime water quality parameter and is attributed due to the presence of nitrates, bicarbonates, sulphates and chlorides of Ca and Mg. The total hardness of the samples range

from 560-700 ppm whereas the permissible limit is 300 ppm. Water is hard in nature in both the samples.

The sulphate ion is one of the most important anion present in natural waters and it produces cathartic effect upon human beings when it is present in excess amounts. The sulphates ion cocentration in the entire area varied from 100-124 ppm. High concentration may be due to seepage of water.

The nitrate ion concentration is very important in public water supplies because it causes methanoglobenemia in children. The concentration varied from 1.064-1.418 ppm which is much below the permissible limit of 45 ppm.

Phosphates are of great importance in drinking waters and the quantity of phosphates in water indicates the degree of pollution of a water body. The phosphates concentration varied from 0.233-0.83 ppm.

Chlorides are considered to be pollution indicating parameter (Krishna Murty, et.al., 1994). In the present study concentration varied from 239.99-359.99 ppm. The high concentration of chlorides imparts salty taste to water. For people who are not accustomed to high chlorides are subjected to laxative effect. Hence, the limit is fixed as 250 ppm at which water will not taste salty. The high concentration of chlorides in the bore well waters of the study area may be due to the seepage of municipal solid waste.

Dissolved oxygen is a vitally important species in water. It is consumed by oxidation of organci matter or reducing agents. It is an important water quality parameter. The optimum value for good water quality is 4.0-6.0 ppm of dissolved oxygen. Lower DO values indicate water pollution. In the present study, in both the sample stations the DO values are with in permissible limits.

The water quality Index in both the samples shown >100 indicates that water is not suitable for drinking purposes because of the presence of oxidizable impurities and salts. However, long term plan is required to assess the water quality including heavy metals during different seasons and also consideration of various activities of the area. The water quality Index value of all the sampling stations have been given in Table No.4.

Table No.4: Water Quality Index (WQI) of Bore Well Waters Collected from Dumping Yard

S.No.	Parametre	SI Values	Wi Value	WiQi S-1	WiQi S-2
1	pH	7.74	0.129	11.96	10.98
2	Hardness	300	0.0033	0.559	0.0699
3.	Calcium	75	0.0133	3.46	4.5
4	Magnesium	30	0.033	36.0	44.0

5	Sulphates	150	0.0066	0.25	0.31
6	Nitrates	45	0.022	2.364	3.151
7	Chemical Oxygen Demand	20	0.05	90.0	70.0
8	Dissolved Oxygen	5	0.2	12	7.6
9	Total Dissolved Solids	500	0.002	0.22	0.20
10	Chlorides	250	0.004	0.38	0.57
			ΣW_i	$\Sigma W_i Q_i$	$\Sigma W_i Q_i$
			0.4632	157.193	141.380

Physico-Chemical Analysis of Soils:

The physico-chemical characteristics of soils of municipal solid waste dumping yard are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Water Quality Index (WQI) of Bore Well waters collected from Dumping Yard

S.No	Parameter	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Average + S.D.
1	pH	8.24	8.12	8.22	8.19+0.064
2	Conductivity (mMhos/cm)	0.804	2.34	0.968	1.37+0.84
3	Organic Carbon %	3.3	3.06	3.0	3.12+0.15
4	Sodium (mg/g)	0.8	1.93	0.72	1.15+0.67
5	Potassuim (mg/g)	1.93	1.74	1.82	1.83+0.09
6	Chlorides (mg/g)	31.99	71.99	37.99	47.32+21.5
7	Sulphates (mg/g)	0.665	0.97	0.665	0.76+0.17
8	Nitrates (mg/g)	0.108	0.024	0.096	0.076+0.045
9	Phosphates (mg/g)	0.069	0.035	0.085	0.063+0.025
10	Calcium (mg/g)	23	28.8	22.8	24.86+3.40
11	Magnesium (mg/g)	4.4	7.2	22.8	11.46+9.91
12	Total Hardness	27.4	36	24	29.13+6.18
13	Organic Matter %	5.68	5.27	5.172	5.0+0.002
14	Available Nitrogen %	0.0238	0.02408	0.0252	0.024+7.41

Note: Sample 1. Solid waste

Sample 2. Soil Solid Waste

The pH of soil varied from 8.12 to 8.24 with an average of 8.19 and is well within the limits. The percentage of Organic Carbon is rich within ranged from 3.00 to 3.3 within an average value 3.12. The organic carbon content is very high and it is due to the presence of various organic constituents of municipal solid waste and various synthesized compounds and derivatives of these materials produced as microbial decomposition. This is further supported by the activity of microbial respiration in terms of available Nitrogen and Organic matter which was reported as 0.024% and 5.0% on an average of 3 samples. The remaining all parameter values are in normal range. The study is preliminary in nature and provides baseline information about the soil quality in municipal dumping yard.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The present study clearly depicts that Hardness, Chlorides, dissolved solids and sulphate are major pollutant of concern which exceeded the permissible standards. The concentrations of pH, Conductivity, Nitrates and Dissolved Oxygen were below the standards prescribed by Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB). The present study further suggests that regular monitoring should be done in various seasons to identify the changes in characteristics of ground water and soil near dump yards.

Improvement of proper waste management options of source reduction, reuse, recycling, composting, storage or disposal must be integrated to ensure safe and effective solid waste management systems at the local, regional, national and International level. Strong public awareness and education programmes must be an integral part of waste management systems. Attitude adjustment towards wastes and wasting resources should be an important part of education programmes. Education can be used to influence public attitude to promote source reduction, reuse and recycling, composting and waste storage. The law and policy should be implemented strictly and huge fines should be imposed if the waste is discarded improperly.

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